

FARABI'S WORK OF FOZIL PEOPLE, THE MORAL VIRTUES OF FOZIL CITY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN THE EDUCATION OF SPIRITUALLY DEVELOPED GENERATION

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Abu Nasr Forobiyning "Fozil odamlar shahri" asarini o'rganish, uning ma'naviyat olamida tutgan o'rnini ko'rsatish, jamiyatni tadrijiy rivojlanishi uchun nihoyatda katta ahamiyatga ega ekanligini chuqur falsafiy va ilmiy farazlar asosida isbotlab berish zarurligi haqida yozilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Fozil shahar, barkamol avlod, zaruriy ehtiyojlar shahri, ayrboshlovchilar shahri, razolat (tubanlik) va badbaxtlik shahri, yevroparastlar shahri, shahvatparastlar shahri, Beqaror shahar.*

АННОТАЦИЯ: *В данной статье говорится о необходимости изучения «Города знатных людей» Абу Насра аль-Фараби, показать его место в духовном мире, доказать на основе глубоких философских и научных гипотез, что он имеет большое значение для постепенное развитие общества.*

Ключевые слова: *город Фазиль, гармонично развитое поколение, город необходимости, город меновщиков, город разврата и нищеты, город европейцев, город похоти, город нестабильности.*

Annotation: *This article deals with the need to study Abu Nasr al-Farabi's "City of Noble People", to show its place in the spiritual world, to prove on the basis of deep philosophical and scientific hypotheses that it is of great importance for the gradual development of society. .*

Key words: *Fazil city, harmoniously developed generation, city of necessities, city of exchangers, city of depravity and misery, city of Europeans, city of lusts, city of instability.*

Farabi's teachings emphasize ignorance and attitudes toward popular culture. It divides the state into virtuous and contradictory states. He believes that science, philosophy, ethics and enlightenment should be in the first place in a virtuous city. Then society will mature, he says. Pharaoh

believes that good deeds, which serve for the perfection of man, are good deeds. He warns people against bad habits such as laziness, idleness, ignorance, ignorance, and lack of profession, which hinder a person's perfection.

Farabi believes that the highest goal of life is to achieve happiness, which is achieved through the study of the world, the acquisition of professions and sciences, and enlightenment.

Commenting on the city, which contradicts the city of Farabi Fozil, these cities (states) include: the city of the ignorant, the city of the dishonest, the exchangers the city is a city of lost, misguided people. The representatives of these cities are some people who are the opposite of the nobles.

Continuing his thoughts on the city of the ignorant, Farabi writes, "The people of the city of the ignorant do not strive for happiness, nor do they know what happiness is, because people in ignorance have never found happiness and do not believe in happiness".

The people of the city of ignorance write about their notions of well-being: they think that lust, prestige, deeds, and fame are true happiness and prosperity. In the eyes of ignorant people, each of these blessings seems to be the purpose of life, happiness. Of course, there are many people in this world who believe that living honestly and cleanly is their life's mission and goal. It is because of such people and their good deeds that spirituality is always stable in this enlightened world. However, there are many people who live far away from such noble qualities and interpret the meaning of life on their own. Unfortunately, they try to feel like the real owners of the world, as if they are living a life of luxury, envy, and happiness.

Of course, those who see such situations and set high goals for themselves may have some doubts and doubts in their hearts. There are so many things in life that make people think. How can this be explained?

We all know that our sacred books and values, the heritage of our great thinker ancestors, always call us to live with honest labor, courage, generosity and humility, but at the same time, a person who strives to follow such calls in life often faces various difficulties, it is not difficult to observe that he even suffers. Admittedly, a person who strives to live with a high level of spirituality still has to overcome many hardships, trials and obstacles. After all, true happiness can be achieved only when all (material and spiritual) blessings are combined. The opposite of these blessings — diseases of the body, poverty, pleasure, pleasures and respect, and lack of prestige — seems to be unhappiness). Pharoah mentions several types of ignorant

cities. One of them is the city of necessities. The people of such a city are limited to what they need only for the body: food, drink, clothing, shelter, sex, and helping each other to achieve this¹.

One of the ignorant cities is the city of exchangers. The inhabitants of the city of exchanges believe that the main purpose of life is to help each other in the pursuit of wealth.

One of the ignorant cities is the city of depravity and misery. The inhabitants of such a city strive only for the pleasure of eating, drinking, sexual intercourse, all kinds of emotional pleasures, pleasures, pleasures.

Pharoah cites the city of Europeans as one of the ignorant cities. The people of this city love to praise each other and raise each other to the sky. They want other nations to honor them, both in word and deed. They want to look great in front of each other or in the eyes of strangers. Farobi cites the capital of the Roman Empire, which sought to conquer the world, as an example of such cities.

One of the ignorant cities is the city of the rulers. The inhabitants of such a city want all nations to be subject to them, and they themselves to be submissive to no one. Their thoughts are on remembrance of victories and futures. Such cities (states) include the United States, Russia, and Europe, which are currently seeking to rule the world.

One of the ignorant cities is the city of lusts. Each of the inhabitants of such a city seeks to satisfy their lusts and low desires as much as they want, without restraining their passions.

The rulers of the cities of ignorance are like the inhabitants of the same cities. In the cities they rule, they are constantly striving to satisfy their personal desires listed above. The training of the people of the ignorant cities is also high serves the stated purposes. If we pay attention, along with the exemplary proverbs about honesty and impurity in our language, there are proverbs such as "Did he find his way, let him beat the blood", "Eat the grapes, do not ask about the garden". Of course, such proverbs are not in vain, they are also an expression of a certain truth. Therefore, we cannot deny that there are people who understand the meaning of life in this way and strive to live on it.

But it seems to me that such statements are fabricated by self-interested people who are indifferent and indifferent to how a person earns wealth and possessions. No one cares whether a person is using his God-given intellect and thinking to shed his wealth, or whether he is gaining it in a crooked, filthy way.

Therefore, when we think about spirituality, we need to analyze this issue in detail and in depth, not only in terms of our positive aspects, but also in terms of such complex aspects.

In short, it is a matter of two opposing views of life.

The first is the life views of people who earn their living by honest work, benefit the country with honest and noble deeds, have a deep understanding of the meaning of life and think not only about the pleasures of today's life, but also about the hereafter and its prosperity. .

The second is the exact opposite approach, that is, without worrying about the meaning of life, without bothering oneself with such questions, and giving only to the sorrows of the soul and the fleeting desires and pleasures. , the views of people who live a light life, who are completely indifferent to their duty to their parents and children, to the country. These are the difficult questions that arise from two different worldviews that have plagued mankind since the beginning of human consciousness. The people of the city of Benomus, like the people of the city of the nobles, know and believe in happiness, truth, creation, intellect, and so on, but do not follow them and live like the inhabitants of the ignorant cities mentioned above.

An unstable city. The theoretical views and practical work of such a city dweller were similar to the views and works of the inhabitants of the city of Fozils in the past, but later foreign ideas slowly entered the country and completely changed the views of its inhabitants.

According to the people of the lost city, happiness can be achieved only after death. However, the perceptions of the people of this city about Allahu ta'âlâ azza wa jalla, his creations, and his active intellect are so confused that they cannot be the basis for honest living, does not reflect the original either.

The first ruler of such a city pretends to be the possessor of divine light, but in reality he is not; he uses deception, hypocrisy, and arrogance to prove his divinity.

The governors of such cities are the opposite of the governors of the city of Fozils. The ways of governing the city are also completely opposite. This idea also applies to the residents of these cities. The successive imams of the Fozii cities embody the spirit of a single eternal leader. Wherever the rulers of many such cities live at the same time, they too will be united in one spirit, and their souls will be one spirit. Some of the people of Fozil are engaged in the study and practice of knowledge that is common to all, while others are engaged in the study and practice of knowledge that only

certain people in a certain position need to know. Each of these people attains happiness through such general and specific knowledge and activities. The longer and better each person engages in activities that lead to happiness, the more perfect his mood will be.

Referring to the views of the people of ignorant and misguided cities, Farabi writes, "We call cities whose people's religious beliefs are based on superstitious, erroneous worldviews ignorant or misguided". Some of them think that some beings are against each other and try to destroy each other. Each of these creatures has such a reserve in the living environment that it protects itself from the opposing being and protects its offspring from extinction. He has the same power in living conditions, through which he loses something against himself and creates a being like himself instead.

Finally, he is endowed with such an ability that he seeks to create a constant good environment in which to live, using a variety of things.

LIST OF REFERENCES:

1. S.Otamurodov, S.Hasanov, J.Ramatov "Fundamentals of spirituality". Tashkent, People's Heritage Publishing House named after A.Qodiriy. 2002, 160 - p
2. Abu Nasr al-Farabi, The City of Noble People. Abdulla Qodiri Publishing House, Tashkent, 1993
3. Khayrullayev M.M. Farabi and his philosophical treatises. Toshkent .1963.
4. Xayrullaev M. Abu Nasr Farabi.Tashkent.1961;
5. Khairullaev M. The second teacher. G`G` Guliston.Tpshkent.1975, №9
6. Khairullaev M. Renaissance and Eastern thinker. T.1971